

Psychological aspects of emotional stress in adaptation to educational activities

Nigora Abdulkakhhorovna Kozimova

Asian International University

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology

Abstract:

This article is about the psychological characteristics of emotional stress in students' adaptation to educational activities the word goes. Also, information is provided about the emotional-emotional state of the students in the first stage and the technical methods used in them and their solutions.

Key words: student psychology, emotional stress, personality, family environment, authoritarian, actual, distress, psychological approach, behavior, correction.

Liberalization, spiritual renewal of society is provided, first of all, by instilling spiritual and moral traditions, humanitarian and democratic values into the minds of the young generation. Free in all respects, he has a high sense of responsibility and duty, recognizes his rights, relies on his own strength and capabilities, and has an independent attitude to the events happening around him.

It is important to create and implement a set of additional measures to bring up citizens who are approachable, who at the same time see their personal interests in harmony with the interests of the country and the people.

is one of the tasks.

A modern person lives in a state of intense stress without his will, and nervous tension accumulates regularly. Some people get out of this situation easily by shouting at the people around them. There are people who, with the strength of their upbringing and culture, absorb everything and thereby harm their health. From a medical point of view, it is possible and necessary to raise a quarrel in such situations, but from the point of view of ethics, it is the opposite.

It follows that a person should make the right decision depending on the situation.

Suppressing emotions is usually the cause of various diseases. Anger, jealousy injures the digestive organs, and grief causes diabetes. If a person lives in constant fear of something, his thyroid function will fail. Nervous tension, negative emotions can lead to hypertension, heart failure and heart attack. Especially in the period of adolescence, the student's desire to define his spiritual world, personal qualities, intellectual potential, abilities, and opportunities increases. It is important to help them understand their feelings, inner experiences, and overcome the difficulties that arise in the right way.

When psychological stress is manifested in changes in various functional systems of the body, its intensity or strength can lead to mood disorders, stomach ulcers or heart attacks. Manifestation of emotional stress can be classified in different ways. However, for psychology, it is appropriate to classify them as follows:

Behavioral reactions.

Reactions in mental activity.

Reactions in the emotional sphere.

Changes in physiological processes.

A similar classification was originally made by D. Nutt in order to study the state of anxiety and worry that can cause emotional tension or stress. D. Nutt distinguished the following four components that create a state of anxiety:

mood (or excitement);
cognitive sphere (unpleasant memories, preconceived ideas, wrong predictions);
physiological signs (tachycardia - acceleration of the pulse, acceleration of sweating,
movement disorders);
behavioral disorders.

Yu.V. Shcherbatikh expresses the behavioral manifestations of stress or emotional tension through the following table:

Psychomotor changes are manifested in excessive tension of muscles, especially facial and neck muscles, hand tremors, breathing rhythm disturbances, voice tremors, reduced speed of sensorimotor reactions, speech disorders, etc. In the experiments conducted by Yu.V. Shcherbatikh, stress and other emotional strains also affect a person's writing. For example, under the influence of a bad mood, the distance between the letters widens, and the width of the letters increases. In a good mood, a person's handwriting is written in small letters, beautifully.

Violation of the daily routine is seen in the reduction of sleep, shifting of working hours to the night period, abandonment of useful habits, inability to find suitable ways to relieve emotional stress.

Changes in professional activity are observed in the large number of errors in the performance of routine actions at the workplace, chronic lack of time, decrease in work efficiency, violation of coordination of movement, loss of accuracy.

Disturbances specific to tasks specific to social roles are manifested in the form of lack of time for relationships with relatives and friends, increased conflicts, decreased sensitivity during communication, and signs of behavior contrary to social rules. Also, a person who is in emotional stress for a long time becomes indifferent to social norms and standards. He may not even care about his appearance. Cutting off relationships with others during times of deep emotional stress leaves the main problem unresolved, creates feelings of guilt and helplessness. According to adolescents, emotional stress inherent in educational activities is associated with a decrease in work ability and an increase in fatigue. The negative effects of emotional stress are also manifested in sleep disturbances, unnecessary haste, and lack of time.

The degree of decrease in work ability and sleep disturbance depends on the influence of many objective and subjective factors.

Some authors do not distinguish between the concepts of "emotional stress" and "emotional strain". Both cases are characterized by changes in facial expressions, defects in the performance of movements, and disturbances in the pronunciation of speech. The analysis of situations presented by these authors shows that it is not about long-term stresses of a classical nature, but about short-term emotional stress. They give the following classification of behavioral reactions that are manifested during emotional stress, which is also part of stress:

impulsive form - excessive excitability, decreased braking activity, error and hasty action;
inhibitory form - increased protective braking due to a decrease in the reserve of the nervous system;
generalizing form - unexpected actions.

During times of stress, usually all areas of intellectual activity - even memory and attention - can change.

Taking into account the above, to protect students and young people from various psychological stresses, to achieve the goal of training competent and competitive personnel

capable of meeting world standards in all respects by providing psychological services in the educational process. allows.

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